

"FORMATION OF COMPETENCIES OF THE EDUCATOR OF THE
PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION".

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Abstract: Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on preschool education and Education" dated December 16, 2019, 2019 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on preschool education and Education" dated December 16, 2019, 2019 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2020 No. 802 "on approval of the state standard of preschool education and education", decree of the Minister of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2019 No. 155 "on the working documents of teachers of state preschool educational organizations", on the implementation of the order in order to ensure the execution of a refresher course based on the requirements for granting, this working Training Program has been developed.

Based on the educational program of the course for the professional development of Educators of the Preschool Educational Organization, which reveals the content and essence of the organization of education targeted at Educators of the Preschool Educational Organization with the personality of the Child, the provision of, the educational program of the module "Competence Approach to the Development of Children" was created.

The principle of ensuring the harmony of education and upbringing with social life must be closely followed in order to enhance the professional competence of educators in the preschool educational organization. It is important to treat a child's development individually, respect his individuality, consider his interests, requirements, and developmental stage, and consider his feelings. The assimilation of the material, formats, resources, and methods used in educational work by educators is accomplished on this basis. Teachers need to be skilled in getting kids involved in social activities. All of this forms the foundation for the content of

educators' spiritual traits. In addition to teaching children about their positive features, preschool educators should have knowledge about how to stop and eradicate harmful traits in behavior.

Children who are new to a preschool educational setting frequently exhibit timidity, whims, and a lack of acclimatization to group life. Eliminating these situations, preparing kids for group life, putting them in communication scenarios, and maintaining their mental peace are some of the crucial jobs of educators. Education professionals have a vital role to play in helping children eliminate their negative character traits, train them to be honest and correct, and develop their will. In doing so, educators ought to employ a group-wide impact strategy. Educators need to acquaint children with the surrounding reality, prepare them for their participation in this process. Only when tasks of clear, moderate complexity are set before children, they show initiative, curiosity, a desire to show activity. As a result, the child develops a sense of responsibility, seeks to justify the Trust expressed by the educator. The ability of children to carry out tasks set for themselves contributes to the regulation of their behavior. As a result of this, character, volitional qualities are strengthened in them.

The instructor eliminates the children's inadequacies by focusing on the positive elements of their behavior and encouraging them. However, it is important to reinforce in the minds of educators that continually focusing on a child's flaws does not produce a fruitful outcome.

The pedagogue-educator must be both friendly and strict in order to shape the conduct of the students. Parents must collaborate closely with caregivers who exhibit shyness, apathy, playfulness, and stubbornness in kid conduct.

Organization and management of the educational process in preschool educational organizations depend heavily on the implementation of cooperation with parents and the community. The decision-making role of the pedagogue-educator in the development of moral qualities in children such as diligence, logicalness, workability, and responsibility is unmatched, and such a responsible task should be realized by them as early as the study process in higher pedagogical educational institutions.

As you can see, preschool education, the tasks set before the educators who operate in it are complex and multifaceted. That is why educators and executive employees are required to systematically work in the field of the basics of the scientific worldview, high moral qualities, the ability to establish the skills and habits of the team, behavior in society.

Students should be made aware of the necessity to rely on specific concepts to ensure the success of the preschool educational process. In order to broaden the spiritual world and worldview of children and to organize them in a methodical

fashion for pedagogical procedures that serve to prepare them for such events, educators should consider the importance of mass events, festive nights, and varied excursions.

When a caregiver is able to attract and interest children in training, the need arises for a greater study of things, subjects, events in them. Of particular importance in this regard are various circles, festive nights, early ones, which are organized in a preschool educational organization. The need for educational work in a preschool educational organization to be carried out based on the knowledge, habits and life experiences that children have previously mastered is given to students. On this basis, they assimilate complex forms of pedagogical influence that they exert on children, harmonize what they are mastering new with previously mastered knowledge, criteria and rules of behavior.

Conducting events consistently is made possible by the idea of systematicity. It is crucial to include activities with a clear, specific relevance and consistency in the pedagogical educator's work plan for the preschool educational organization. First and foremost, this system ought to symbolize the preschool educational system and work to instill in kids a sense of patriotism, spirituality, and morality that is both universal and national. Instead, it should highlight the unique aspects of the children's group's work, the traditions that they have created, and the educator-unique educator's working style and technique.

Of particular importance for educators is the organization of the activities of educators and the development of methods that contribute to independence and initiative in them. It is known that life experience in Educators of preschool educational organizations will not be sufficiently developed. Therefore, their movement, educational and educational activities need the management of teachers and educators.

Currently, the educator-first educator's responsibility is to motivate students and foster their development of activity and desire for independence. The educator-educator should offer pedagogical flexibility in the activities of educators, ensuring their independence, and fostering each child's achievement. Every child's development depends on this. The quality and efficacy of preschool education are ensured by the abilities of educators, who are drawn to engaging activities and receive regular stimulation while working on tasks.

A challenging pedagogical challenge is managing the pedagogical operations of preschool educational institutions. Preschool education must take into account the unique traits of each kid as well as their age-related characteristics. The unique qualities of the students in each group determine the subject matter, delivery methods, and organizational strategies used in the preschool educational process. The age-related characteristics of children cause these indicators to change.

When choosing the content of educational and educational activities of teachers and educators of preschool educational organizations, it is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of children. Depending on the age groups of educators, the forms and methods of Education also change. Educators of preschool educational organizations are required to provide a wider interpretation of concepts and information. Children are taught, first of all, the need to follow the norms of behavior. That is why, starting from the process of preschool education, the necessary norms are embedded in the child's behavior. In preschool educational organizations, in the process of socialization of children, they are subjected to pedagogical influence with the help of Game, persuasion, methods of prohibition.

Education professionals are seen as the direct managers and organizers of the everyday activities in preschool educational organizations. An essential component of the work of pedagogical educators is ensuring that the demands placed on educators are in line with their capacities.

When too complex tasks are set in front of children, a mood arises in them to get tired of training, not to believe in themselves. In the process of preschool education, it is important to take into account the specificity of the nervous system of children. It is necessary to calm a child with tense nerves, encourage tranquility, and in timid children, encourage activity, cheer him up. It is necessary to realize their talents by encouraging children who are separated from their groupmates by their ingenuity, a tendency to creative activity. Alternatively, the further development of positive qualities in children, the enrichment of their worldview is of particular importance. To do this, in the process of pedagogical practice, it is necessary that teachers and educators of future preschool educational organizations study each educator in detail, be able to identify specific aspects of development in them. In the process of preschool education, it is necessary to take into account the gender characteristics inherent in each of the boys and girls.

It is necessary for preschool educational organizations to develop professional abilities, attributes inherent in pedagogy, in order to succeed in their activities in the training of educators, in the process of higher pedagogical education. Preschoolers have intense curiosity. They frequently bombard their parents and caregivers with inquiries and demand detailed responses. They learn a lot by listening to the radio, seeing different multiplicative movies on television, and reading fairy tales and puzzles. As a result, they are interested in knowing all things, many questions arise and turn to adults with questions they have. Educators should be able to calmly answer their questions clearly. Hesitation, speaking incorrectly, getting out of the situation in search of opportunities undermines the image of the educator, a mood of distrust of the educator arises among children. That is why educators need to constantly search, gain independent knowledge, be

aware of everyday events. They are required to monitor news and research in the field of fiction, art, science and Technology, Technology. Only then can it satisfy the cognitive needs of its wards, provide effective pedagogical activity in perspective.

The essence of the concept of "competence". In the context of market relations, each Specialist must have professional competence and continuously improve it in order to survive the intense rivalry that holds a prominent position on the labor market. What then is competence? What characteristics form the foundation of professional competence? The ability of the educator to demonstrate his competencies is essential. This and related concepts are mentioned at the same time.

"Competence" the concept came into the field of education as a result of psychological research. For this reason, competence refers to "non-traditional situations, how a specialist behaves in unexpected cases, enters into communication, behaves in a new way in interaction with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, owns a plan for moving in consistently developing and complex processes".

The concept of "competence" in content is interpreted as "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activity, the manifestation of a high level of professional qualifications, skills and talent". Competence is the ability, Ability and ability of an individual to apply the knowledge, practical skills and abilities acquired by him in his chosen profession to practice, and the ability to independently solve professional problems. Competencies are requirements. Competence is a manifestation of the fulfillment of these requirements.

Professional competence is the integration of integrative information and activities in each separate direction, not the acquisition by an expert of unique knowledge and skills. Additionally, competence calls for the ongoing development of specialized knowledge, the study of new information, the capacity to comprehend critical societal requirements, the pursuit of new information, and the capacity to process and apply it in one's work.